

*Josephus and the Murder of James:
An Argument Against Some Common Wisdom*

Chrissy M. Hansen
University of Nebraska-Kearney

ABSTRACT

Josephus' testimonia on the life of Jesus are among the most scrutinized texts in antiquity. Until recently, however, commentators have let the James passage (Ant. 20.200) go relatively unscathed, instead opting to assume authenticity without much comment. This article challenges the consensus viewpoint on the James passage, bringing to light several concerns regarding the style of the passage and its transmission, both of which point to Christian redaction. The article argues instead that Eusebius likely interpolated the passage.

Keywords: Josephus, Antiquities, historical Jesus, James, brother of the Lord, Testimonium Flavianum

INTRODUCTION

While the *Testimonium Flavianum* has been scrutinized for its origins, endless recensions, and range of potential Christian interpolations, Josephus' passage on James in *Antiquities* 20.200 is often regarded as authentic with comparatively little justification. The passage maintains consistent support among academics not because of what it is, but because of what it does not appear to be; it does not adhere to Christian tradition, is not consistent with how Christians referred to Jesus' siblings, and bears little to no outward signs of interpolative action. By far the most comprehensive support in favor of its authenticity, recently, has come from Alice Whealey and James Carleton Paget.¹ Those who argue against the passage's authenticity have largely restricted their argumentation to limited data; scholars have neither conducted thorough investigations of the passage and its recensions, nor analyzed wider trends in how Josephus used adelphonyms or other relevant information.²

¹ Alice Whealey, "Josephus, Eusebius of Caesarea, and the Testimonium Flavianum," in *Josephus und das Neue Testament*, ed. Christfried Böttrich, Jens Herzer, and Torsten Reiprich (Tübingen: Mohr Siebeck, 2007), 73–116. See also Alice Whealey, *Josephus on Jesus: The Testimonium Flavianum Controversy from Late Antiquity to Modern Times* (Frankfurt: Peter Lang, 2003), 2–5; and James Carleton Paget, "Some Observations on Josephus and Christianity," *Journal of Theological Studies* 52, no. 2 (2001): 539–624.

² The only exception here has been Nicholas List, "The Death of James the Just Revisited," *Journal of Early Christian Studies* 32, no. 1 (2024): 17–44. However, List does not produce any thorough investigation on the function of adelphonymics in Josephus' work.

Correspondence should be addressed to Chrissy M. Hansen at cmehans2020@gmail.com.

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Taking its authenticity largely for granted, most academics have summarily dismissed the growing number of challengers who see this passage as being at least partially interpolated by Christians.³

I will argue that the passage is much more likely to be inauthentic, and in fact that there is little reason for accepting the entire phrase τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ (“the brother of Jesus, called Christ”) as authentically Josephan.⁴ Instead, I propose that on the basis of Origen’s (errant) claims, the passage was interpolated, probably by Eusebius or someone close to his time, and that all resulting quotations and manuscript traditions likely arise from this same Eusebian origin point. This study will also highlight previously undiscussed evidence for interpolation, including a detailed overview of Josephus’ usage of introductory adelphonims and an analysis of known quotations and usages of the *Ant.* 20.200 passage throughout Late Antiquity and the early Middle Ages, which scholars have largely neglected.⁵

STYLISTIC PROBLEMS IN *ANTIQUITIES* 20.200

There is one immediately apparent stylistic anomaly in the text: the term Χριστὸς (“Christ”), which is uncharacteristic of Josephus. There is only one other occasion of this word in the *textus receptus* of Josephus’ *Antiquities* and that is in the infamous *Testimonium Flavianum* (*Ant.* 18.63–64), which was clearly tampered with. Many following John P. Meier, therefore, would contend the mention of Χριστὸς is inauthentic.⁶ As William O.

³ For noteworthy scholarship on this, see Ken Olson, “Eusebius and the ‘Testimonium Flavianum’,” *Catholic Biblical Quarterly* 61, no. 2 (1999): 305–22; Nicholas P. L. Allen, “Josephus on James the Just? A re-evaluation of *Antiquitates Judaicae* 20.9.1,” *Journal of Early Christian History* 7, no. 1 (2017): 1–27; Li Yaming, *Lishi shang zhenshi de yesu* (Taibei shi: Wunan tushu chuban gufen youxian gongsi, 2017), 41–2. Many of these challenges arise from the “mythicist” crowd; see Raphael Lataster, *Questioning the Historicity of Jesus: Why a Philosophical Analysis Elucidates the Historical Discourse* (Leiden: Brill, 2019), 199–202; Robert M. Price, *Killing History: Jesus in the No-Spin Zone* (Amherst: Prometheus, 2014), 243–44; Hermann Detering, *Falsche Zeugen: Außerchristliche Jesuszeugnisse auf dem Prüfstand* (Aschaffenburg: Alibri Verlag, 2011), 22–29; Léon Herrmann, *Chrestos: Témoignages païens et juifs sur le christianisme du premier siècle* (Bruxelles: Latomus, 1970), 97–104.

⁴ This contrasts with others who have proposed partial interpolations of just λεγομένου Χριστοῦ. See Richard Carrier, “Origen, Eusebius, and the Accidental Interpolation in Josephus, *Jewish Antiquities* 20.200,” *Journal of Early Christian Studies* 20, no. 4 (2012): 489–514.

⁵ I will be using online databases, including the Perseus *Scaife* viewer and *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* (TLG). Numbering for TLG sources is per their system.

⁶ John P. Meier, *A Marginal Jew: The Roots of the Problem and the Person* (New York: Doubleday, 1991), 61–69. Others aver that the Latin and Syriac/Arabic instances of downplayed language with ‘believed to be the Christ’ indicate it was original. Space does not permit a thorough response, however it should be noted that the Latin tradition all stems from Jerome, see David B. Levenson and Thomas R. Martin, “The Latin Translations of Josephus on Jesus, John the Baptist, and James: Critical Texts of the Latin Translation of the *Antiquities* and Rufinus’ Translation of Eusebius’ *Ecclesiastical History* Based on Manuscripts and Early Printed Editions,” *Journal for the Study of Judaism* 45 (2014): 1–79 at 25–26. Jerome’s account is possibly contaminated by Pseudo-Hegesippus’ *De Excidio* 2.12 paraphrase (itself descended from Eusebius, see below), see Richard Matthew Pollard, “The *De Excidio* of ‘Hegesippus’ and the Reception of Josephus in the Early Middle Ages,” *Vivator* 46.2 (2015): 65–100 at 83. This is noteworthy, as *De Excidio* probably also depends on Eusebius, see Carson Bay, *Biblical Heroes and Classical Culture in Christian Late Antiquity* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2022). Thus, we can discount the Latin transmission. The Syriac/Arabic versions almost

Walker notes, in cases where we are dealing with an already altered text (in his case the Pauline epistles), the burden of proof for determining an interpolation is significantly reduced.⁷ The addition of this questionable language in the James passage justifies pursuing the issue further. If the *Testimonium Flavianum* reference is inauthentic (or, at the very least, the reference to Jesus as “Christ”), then this unexplained term (Χριστὸς) has no purpose in *Ant.* 20.200. The term would certainly need some explanation, as Josephus’ gentile audience⁸ would have no understanding of it.⁹ Further, as Nicholas List observes, it is strange that Josephus would refer to James by reference to an obscure figure (Jesus) mentioned two books and several hundred lines ago.¹⁰

After having reviewed all of Josephus’ extant works, there is a general trend that appears regarding the formation and usage of adelphonims. List brought up Josephus’ general use of adelphonims to justify his argument that the *Ant.* 20.200 passage originally read “the brother of Jesus, named James,” and that the message of “who was called Christ” was a gloss.¹¹ For this he cites a few examples, including where a figure is cited by reference to a previously un-introduced brother. However, notably, all of Josephus’ other adelphonims starkly contrast with the *Antiquities* 20.200 passage. For instance, List cites 20.137 where Josephus introduces

certainly stem from the Syriac of Eusebius, which originally read “he was the Christ.” This, then, must be a later gloss, possibly resulting from the rising influence of Islam, which also accounts for Michael the Syrian and Agapius over-emphasizing the death of Jesus, see Alice Whealey, “The Testimonium Flavianum in Syriac and Arabic,” *New Testament Studies* 54, no. 4 (2008): 573–90. Obviously, Christians were capable of redacting the “he was the Christ” to sound more natural, as was done in manuscripts of Rufinus’ translation of *Historia Ecclesiastica*, see Levenson and Martin, “The Latin Translations of Josephus,” 25–26. Martino Diez, “Les antiquités gréco-romaines entre al-Makīn ibn al-Amīd et Ibn Ḥaldūn. Notes pour une histoire de la tradition,” *Studia graeco-arabica* 3 (2013): 121–40 at 134–35 also notes Al-Makin’s usage and quotation of Agapius. Claudia Setzer, *Jewish Responses to Early Christians: History and Polemics, 30–150 C.E.* (Minneapolis: Fortress, 1994), 211n13 proposes Agapius’ version is just a poor rendering from Syriac to Arabic. We also see evidence of this redaction in Cedrenus’ *Compendium Historiarum*, which copies George Hamartolos’ *Testimonium Flavianum* but changes ὁ Χριστὸς οὗτος ἦν το πολλοὺς γὰρ καὶ ἀπὸ Ἑλλήνων ἠγάγετο Χριστός despite copying the passage verbatim up to that point. As such, there is no compelling reason to consider “believed to be the Christ” to be authentic or to prefer it as original over “he was the Christ” (especially since “believed to be the Christ” is lacking in all Greek renditions of the passage). Sozomen, *Historia Ecclesiastica* 1.1.5 renders it Χριστὸν δὲ περιφανῶς ὀνομάζει (“he evidently calls him Christ”), however this is a paraphrase and unlike Cedrenus, not an otherwise close quotation.

⁷ William O. Walker, “The Burden of Proof in Identifying Interpolations in the Pauline Letters,” *New Testament Studies* 33, no. 4 (1987): 610–18 at 615.

⁸ For Josephus having a gentile audience, see Jan N. Bremmer, “Ioudaismos, Christianismos and the Parting of the Ways,” in *Jews and Christians – Parting Ways in the First Two Centuries CE? Reflections on the Gains and Losses of a Model*, ed. Jens Schröter, Benjamin A. Edsall, and Joseph Verheyden (Berlin: Walter De Gruyter, 2021), 57–87 at 70.

⁹ As evident from early Greco-Roman sources, they often presumed that Χριστὸς/Christus was a name and not a title, see Pliny the Younger, *Ep.* 10.96; Tacitus, *Annals* 15.44. Also relevant would be the several references to Jesus by Galen, see Rebecca Flemming, “Galen and the Christians: Texts and Authority in the Second Century AD,” in *Christianity in the Second Century: Themes and Developments*, ed. James Carleton Paget and Judith Lieu (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017), 171–87. Even stronger evidence would be the consistent confusion of *Christus* with *Chrestus*, see Walter Shandruk, “The Interchange of ι and η in the Spelling of Χριστ- Words in Egyptian Papyri,” *Bulletin of the American Society of Papyrologists* 47 (2010): 205–19.

¹⁰ List, “The Death of James the Just Revisited,” 21n17.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 21.

“Felix Pallans’ brother” (Φήλικα Πάλλαντος ἀδελφὸν).¹² There are two issues here. Firstly, Felix is mentioned first and is the focal point unlike in 20.200, which seems to presume prior knowledge of a character (i.e., the Jesus from the *Testimonium Flavianum*). Secondly, while Josephus occasionally identifies figures by otherwise unknown persons, he does not introduce a character by their brother, unless their brother was previously introduced.¹³ A review of Josephus’ texts produces no exceptions to these trends.

To determine any workable parallels to the James passage, I surveyed the whole *Antiquities* for parallel constructions to *Ant.* 20.200 and found none. Instead, when adelphonymics are utilized, the pertinent subject figure is either named first, or has been previously introduced (neither of which apply to James).¹⁴ As far as I am aware, there are no parallels for introducing a character for the first time by an adelphonymic and then by the name of the individual in question in *Antiquities*. One example which List does not consider, is αὐτοῦ ἀδελφῶ ὁμοπατρίῳ ὄντι Ἐλιακείμῳ (“his brother on his father’s side named Eliakim”) in *Ant.* 10.82. However, this is unlike the passage in *Ant.* 20.200 for numerous reasons, the biggest being that the subject is performing an act on his own brother, making the reference to his status as brother (coming before the name) natural. Additionally, it would not work to just call him “his brother, Eliakim” because of their complicated familial relationship which required more exposition; Eliakim is introduced prior to this in *Antiquities* and discussed at length.

The only other examples I have found bearing any similarity is *Ant.* 11.298 which introduces a figure as ἀδελφὸς ἦν τῷ Ἰωάννῃ Ἰησοῦς (“John’s brother Joshua”), but John was previously introduced (11.297). Similarly, 11.302 has Manasses introduced as a brother,

¹² Ibid.

¹³ In fact, I was only able to find one example where a previously un-introduced figure is introduced for the first time by relation to a brother who was named first: *Jewish War* 1.130 (τὸν ἀδελφὸν τὸν Ἀντιπάτρου Φαλλίωνα). However, in this case, Antipater (the brother Phallion is identified by) was the primary subject and already long introduced. Thus, it differs from *Ant.* 20.200 significantly.

¹⁴ *Ant.* 1.154 (Sarah’s brother, Lot, named prior); *Ant.* 2.17, 2.35, 38, 167 (Joseph’s brothers); *Ant.* 4.21 (Moses’ brother); *Ant.* 4.152 (grandson of Moses’ brother); *Ant.* 5.235 (brother named Jotham, who is previously introduced in 5.234); *Ant.* 6.178 (eldest brother Eliab, introduced in 6.161); *Ant.* 7.11 (cf. 6.311); *Ant.* 7.109 (Ἀβεσσαῖον τὸν Ἰωάβου τοῦ ἀρχιστρατήγου ἀδελφόν); *Ant.* 11.79 (Zodmiel the brother of Judas); *Ant.* 11.322 Manasses, a brother of the high priest Judas (Μανασσῆ τοῦ τῶν Ἰουδαίων ἀρχιερέως Ἰαδδοῦ ἀδελφόν); *Ant.* 12.44 only has an adelphonymic in some English translations (ὁ ἀδελφὸς αὐτοῦ Ἐλεάζαρος), where the name Simon is added for clarification; *Ant.* 12.238 (Joshua brother of Onias, previously introduced in 12.237); *Ant.* 13.222 has Ἀντιόχου τοῦ Δημητρίου ἀδελφοῦ; *Ant.* 13.369 Ἀντίοχος ὁ Σελεύκου ἀδελφός; *Ant.* 13.387 talks of Antiochus and uses an adelphonymic, but only after his name and surname are written (Ἀντίοχος ὁ κληθεὶς Διόνυσος ἀδελφὸς ὢν Φιλίππου); *Ant.* 14.33 mentions Phallion, the brother of Antipater, but names Phallion first (Φαλλίων ὁ Ἀντιπάτρου ἀδελφός); *Ant.* 14.121 introduces Phasael and Joseph, and Joseph is later identified with an adelphonymic τὸν ἀδελφὸν τὸν Ἡρώδου Ἰώσηπον (*Ant.* 14.390) and Phasael is in 15.12 (τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἡρώδου Φασάηλον); *Ant.* 15.184 introduces Pheroras, and in 16.194 he is identified with the adelphonymic τοῦ βασιλέως ἀδελφὸς Φερώρας and again in 17.257 as τοῦ Ἡρώδου ἀδελφοῦ Φασάηλου; *Ant.* 18.106 Philip’s death is remarked upon (after he has been discussed frequently) by referring to him as the brother of Herod; *Ant.* 17.70 has Θευδίωνος μητρὸς Ἀντιπάτρου ἀδελφοῦ; *Ant.* 18.151 Aristobulus is designated as Agrippa’s brother but again names Aristobulus first and uses a full adelphonymic in 18.273 (Ἀριστόβουλος ὁ Ἀγρίππου τοῦ βασιλέως ἀδελφός); *Ant.* 18.342 has Ἀνιλαῖος ὁ τοῦ Ἀσιναίου ἀδελφός; *Ant.* 20.104 again mentions Herod brother of Agrippa (ὁ τοῦ μεγάλου βασιλέως Ἀγρίππα ἀδελφός); *Ant.* 20.137 Felix brother of Pallans (Φήλικα Πάλλαντος ἀδελφόν); *Ant.* 20.148 Germanicus the brother of Caesar (Γερμανικὸς ὁ Καίσαρος ἀδελφός); *Ant.* 20.225 Aaron brother of Moses (Ἀαρὼνα τὸν Μωυσέως ἀδελφόν).

but not with an adelphonym. *Ant.* 20.75 has τοῦ βασιλέως ἀδελφὸς Μονόβαζος, but Monobazus was already introduced at this point (20.18–20). *Ant.* 17.225 contains τὸν ἀδελφὸν τὸν Νικολάου Πτολεμαῖον, in which Ptolemy is identified but only after Nicolaus. However, as with the other cases (unlike James), Ptolemy had been previously identified (*Ant.* 17.195).

Expanding beyond *Antiquities*, the only close and potential counterexample is *Jewish War* 1.130 τὸν ἀδελφὸν τὸν Ἀντιπάτρου Φαλλίωνα, where Phallion is introduced for the first time. However, unlike the James passage, Phallion is introduced by way of an already known sibling. Thus, using this as a parallel still undermines the authenticity of 20.200 (necessitating a prior Jesus be mentioned, i.e., the dubious *Testimonium Flavianum*). This singular example demonstrates just how unlikely and awkward this phraseology is for Josephus normally. Even more importantly, in all cases where similar examples occur (i.e., where Josephus introduces a character by first noting their relationship to a sibling), they utilize a previously introduced figure (the brother). As a result, based on Josephus' usage of adelphonymics, the *Ant.* 20.200 passage *must* presume the existence of the *Testimonium Flavianum* for the adelphonym to make sense; we cannot see the James passage as independent from the known tampering of *Antiquities* 18.63–64, as it needs the *Testimonium* to be coherent.

THE PROBLEM OF ORIGEN'S TESTIMONY

The first time James is mentioned in connection with Josephus is in the works of Origen. In his *Contra Celsum* and his *Commentary on Matthew*, Origen refers to a passage on James three times. His claims are, however, suspect. Origen claims that Josephus ascribed the fall of Jerusalem and its capture by Vespasian to the martyrdom of James the brother of Jesus (none of which is in our *textus receptus*) and appears to loosely paraphrase our specific section:

- (1) Ἰακώβου τοῦ δικαίου, ὃς ἦν ἀδελφὸς Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ (Origen, *Contra Celsum* 1.47; Eusebius, *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.20) ["James the Just, who was the brother of Jesus who is called Christ"]
- (2) Ἰάκωβον τὸν δίκαιον, τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ (Origen, *Contra Celsum* 2.13) [James the Just, the brother of Jesus, who is called Christ"]
- (3) Ἰακώβον τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ (Origen, *Commentary on Matthew* 10.17) ["James, the brother of Jesus, who is called Christ"]

As List notes, Origen does not quote our *textus receptus*, but offers a paraphrase which does not align with our text. We can find several variations from the currently received version. Specifically, the name of James is prior to the mention of Jesus in these passages. In two of Origen's apparent references, he refers to James as "the just/righteous" as well.

While some have opined that Origen's version is potentially authentic and thus our *textus receptus* is inauthentic,¹⁵ the more prudent solution in my view is that Origen is simply

¹⁵ Sabrina Inowlocki, "Did Josephus Ascribe the Fall of Jerusalem to the Murder of James, Brother of Jesus?" *Revue des études juives* 170, no. 1–2 (2011): 21–49.

mistaken about the contents of Josephus' work and was not a careful (or perhaps a disingenuous) peruser of Josephus' *Antiquities*. To the contrary, Origen misrepresents Josephus on multiple occasions, which should leave us in doubt that he was familiar with his work at all, or lead us to assume that he was fine with extrapolating upon and adding to Josephus' words.¹⁶ Both possibilities should give us pause regarding *Ant.* 20.200.

Many aver that Origen would not use the language of λεγομένου Χριστοῦ or similar for Jesus as it was insufficiently reverent and either implied distance or a potentially negative connotation (denoting Jesus as a "so-called" Messiah).¹⁷ This assumption is invalid, as it implies that ancient Christian authors were not capable of imagining how their interlocutors or non-Christians would talk about Jesus when, in fact, we know that they could and did quite frequently. This very language is utilized in such cases.¹⁸ It should also be noted that Origen uses similar phrasing to describe Jesus as the son of God (καὶ Χριστὸς εἶναι λεγόμενος τοῦ θεοῦ) in a purely reverential setting (*Contra Celsum* 4.28 per Ken Olson).¹⁹ This language is also used in scripture (Matt. 1:16, 27:17; John 4:25, cf. 9:11), which Origen quotes or refers to on numerous occasions.²⁰ List aptly writes that, "If it was good enough for author of Matthew, it was certainly good enough for a Christian redactor of Josephus."²¹ In fact, given that the phrase so often occurs in Christian literature, there is no reason to think that λεγομένου Χριστοῦ would make Origen think Josephus questioned Jesus' status as the Messiah, even though he did. Thus, following List, it would make more sense of

¹⁶ Wataru Mizugaki, "Origen and Josephus," in *Josephus, Judaism, and Christianity*, ed. Louis H. Feldman and Gohei Hata (Leiden: Brill, 1987), 325–37; Heinz Schreckenberg and Kurt Schubert, *Jewish Historiography and Iconography in Early and Medieval Christianity* (Minneapolis: Fortress, 1992), 57–63. Origen's imprecise and inaccurate citations are rather frequent. Schreckenberg proposes it was a result of Origen's dictation style, where he likely had no copy of Josephus in front of him.

¹⁷ Whealey, "Josephus," 111.

¹⁸ Justin Martyr, *Dialogue with Trypho* 32 places λεγόμενος Χριστός (here it is derogatory) in the mouth of Trypho; Ps.-Clement, *Homiliae* 18.4 puts λεγομένου Χριστοῦ in the mouth of Simon Magus. Alexander, *Inventio crucis* 4037.27 (TLG) puts ὁ λεγόμενος Χριστὸς in the mouth of Pilate.

¹⁹ Olson, "Eusebius and the 'Testimonium Flavianum'," 316 also lists Justin Martyr, *First Apology* 30 where Justin responds to an imaginary critic replying καὶ τὸν παρ' ἡμῶν λεγόμενον Χριστόν ("whom we call Christ"). In addition to those Olson listed, one can also note Eusebius, *Demonstratio Evangelica* 4.12 reverentially has ὁ Χριστὸς τοῦ θεοῦ, νικηφόρος λεγόμενος ("the Christ of God, called victor"). See also Eusebius, *Generalis elementaria introductio* 3.31. The latter is per *Sciafe* viewer run by Perseus Digital Library. I have also found *Dialogus Timothei et Aquilae* 17.3a.3–4 (TLG) which utilizes part of Matthew 27:22 to introduce and discuss Jesus (τὸν Ἰησοῦν τὸν λεγόμενον Χριστόν or "Jesus the one called Christ").

²⁰ Origen, *Commentarii in Evangelium Joannis* 1.5.29 and 1.21.126 (John 4:25); Origen, *Contra Celsum*, praef.2 (Matthew 27:22); Origen, *Scholia in Matthew* 27.11 (Matthew 27:22); Origen, *Commentariorum Series in Evangelium Matthaei* (Mt. 22.34–27.63), chap. 121 (Matthew 27:22). Numberings are all per *Sciafe* viewer run by Perseus Digital Library.

²¹ List, "The Death of James the Just Revisited," 26n39. We can see that other Christian sources also utilized these passages, see Gelasius, *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.24.17 (Matthew 1:16); in *Suda* s.v. Νέρων (nu 254) references John 19:38. The above numberings are per *Sciafe* viewer run by Perseus Digital Library. Using the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae*, I was also able to find John Chrysostom, *Homiliae in Joannem* 59.190.38–39 (John 4:25); John Chrysostom, *In Samaritanam* 59.540.63–64 and 59.541.13 (both referring to John 4:25); Cyrillus, *Exposito Psalmos* 69.981.33–34 (John 4:25); Cyrillus, *Commentarius in Isaiam prophetam* 70.1312.18–19 (John 4:25). See also Eustathius, *Commentarius in hexaemeron* 772.8 (Matthew 1:16); *Dialogus Timothei et Aquilae* 17.17.1 (Matthew 1:16); Athanasius, *Sermo de descriptione deiparae* 28.949.30–31 (referencing Matthew 27:17).

Origen's claim that Josephus rejected Jesus as the Messiah (*Contra Celsum* 1.47) to at least omit λεγομένου Χριστοῦ from the text.²²

This was certainly language which Christians could (and did) place in the mouths of nonbelievers, and this is likewise the context of all three times which Origen refers to this passage in Josephus. The first two occasions occur with the specific goal of countering an anti-Christian polemicist, giving him ample motivation to construct this phraseology.

Given this, Origen does not stand as a reliable witness that *Ant.* 20.200 originally contained any reference to James as "the brother of Jesus called Christ." The fact that he renders it in three different ways (none of which match our *textus receptus*), has motive for constructing the phrase, and abused Josephus as a source elsewhere means that Origen is simply unreliable. The insertion of this explanatory note would have likewise been an easy mistake for Origen to make. If there was a figure named "James" (with some other patronymic or title,²³ or more probably standing alone²⁴) in book 20, and it was also not far from the Temple Destruction being mentioned at the end of book 20 (and in fact is part of Josephus' description of a series of events that led to the Jewish War and the destruction of Jerusalem²⁵), Origen could have easily seen this name and mentally made the connection. This connection would be made even stronger by this James also being stoned, which was consistent with Christian beliefs.²⁶ As there are only two people named James in all of book 20, and since the first one (20.103) was executed far too early, then 20.200 would have been the only plausible figure.

INTERPOLATION AND EUSEBIUS

The first author to provide a full quotation of the James passage in context is Eusebius in his *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.22. However, before discussing this it is worth noting that Eusebius, unlike in our current *textus receptus*, ascribes to Josephus *three* separate attestations of Jesus, including two of James the Just. The first reference is cribbed directly from Origen, where Eusebius writes:

²² List, "The Death of James the Just Revisited," 24n23.

²³ Allen, "Josephus on James the Just?" 14 proposes any patronymic could have existed there. Carrier, "Origen, Eusebius, and the Accidental Interpolation," argues the patronymic "son of Damneus" was present. Both seem unnecessary and perhaps overcomplicate interpolation theories.

²⁴ Josephus was inconsistent in his application of patronymics and similar. For instance, Josephus mentions one Epaphroditus in *Ant.* 1.8 who receives no other qualifications or identification. *Ant.* 10.59 mentions an aristocrat named Salloum but provides no further details on who this person was or their connections. As a result, we need not suppose that this James was clearly identified in the text.

²⁵ List, "The Death of James the Just Revisited," 18–22.

²⁶ *Ibid.*, 32–8.

ταῦτα δὲ²⁷ συμβέβηκεν Ἰουδαίοις κατ' ἐκδίκησιν Ἰακώβου τοῦ δικαίου, ὃς ἦν ἀδελφὸς Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ, ἐπειδήπερ δικαιοτάτον αὐτὸν ὄντα οἱ Ἰουδαῖοι²⁸ ἀπέκτειναν (*Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.20)

These things happened to the Judeans to avenge James the Just, the brother of Jesus who is called Christ. For the Judeans slew him, although he was a most righteous man. [translation mine]

This is lifted almost verbatim from *Contra Celsum* 1.47:

ταῦτα συμβεβηκέναι²⁹ τοῖς³⁰ Ἰουδαίοις κατ' ἐκδίκησιν Ἰακώβου τοῦ δικαίου, ὃς ἦν ἀδελφὸς Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ, ἐπειδήπερ δικαιοτάτον αὐτὸν ὄντα ἀπέκτειναν.

Not finding this in Josephus' original work, but clearly attempting to produce as many pieces of evidence for the death of James as possible, Eusebius ascribes Origen's summary to the mouth of Josephus entirely on the former's authority.³¹

After this, Eusebius finally quotes the extant passage more or less as it is contained in our *textus receptus*:³²

ἄτε δὴ οὖν τοιοῦτος ὢν ὁ Ἄνανος, νομίσας ἔχειν καιρὸν ἐπιτήδειον διὰ τὸ τεθνάναι μὲν Φῆστον, Ἀλβῖνον δ' ἔτι κατὰ τὴν ὁδὸν ὑπάρχειν, καθίζει συνέδριον κριτῶν, καὶ παραγαγὼν εἰς αὐτὸν τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ, τοῦ Χριστοῦ λεγομένου, Ἰάκωβος ὄνομα αὐτῷ, καὶ τινὰς ἑτέρους, ὡς παρανομησάντων κατηγορίαν ποιησάμενος, παρέδωκεν λευσθησομένους. (Josephus apud Eusebius, *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.22)

Thus his character led Ananus to think that he had a suitable opportunity through the fact that Festus was dead and Albinus still on his way. He summoned a council of judges, brought before it the brother of Jesus, the so-called Christ, whose name was

²⁷ Origen lacks δὲ.

²⁸ Origen lacks οἱ Ἰουδαῖοι.

²⁹ Eusebius combines these two words into συμβέβηκεν.

³⁰ Eusebius lacks τοῖς.

³¹ Adolf Hilgenfeld, *Historisch-kritische Einleitung in das Neue Testament* (Leipzig: Feus's Verlag, 1875), 526 claimed that this pseudo-Josephan passage was in fact authentic and that it was inexplicably deleted from Christian manuscripts. This claim would go on to cause some confusion for later writers. Inowlocki, "Did Josephus Ascribe the Fall of Jerusalem," regards the Origen passage as having been original. Both positions are unlikely.

³² Cf. the Syriac translation of both passages in William Wright and Norman McLean, eds., *The Ecclesiastical History of Eusebius in Syriac* (Cambridge: University Press, 1898), 104–6.

James, and some others, on the accusation of breaking the law and delivered them to be stoned.³³

Most differences between these versions are minor textual variations,³⁴ but Eusebius' is distinct from Origen's in one way: the reference to "the brother of Jesus called Christ" occurs *prior* to the mention of James in Eusebius' version (and the *textus receptus*), while Origen's references always occur *after* the mention of James, even in his version which is most closely aligned with the *textus receptus* (*Commentary on Matthew* 10.17).

This is potential evidence that τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ was mobile, i.e., the only static part of the passage was the mention of the name "James." Origen and Eusebius attribute τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ to Josephus in two different fashions. Both of them locate the only possible figure this could be, i.e., *Ant.* 20.200, and so ascribe these words to Josephus, but in different places.³⁵ Origen does so by simply extracting the name James, and then placing the rest afterward, which is also the more natural place to put them (and which he is able to do because he is not quoting the passage directly, but summarizing and expanding it with his own traditional interpretations), while Eusebius puts them prior to James' name. The reason for this mobility was probably the inclusion of ὄνομα αὐτῶ ("whose name was") in the original text followed by καὶ τινὰς ἑτέροισι ("and some others"), which precluded Eusebius from simply adding τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ immediately after as Origen did. As a result, it had to be added prior, leading to the awkward construction which, as noted before, is not paralleled elsewhere (unless we presume its reliance on the highly questionable *Testimonium Flavianum*). List already provides evidence that Josephus could refer to otherwise unknown people without clarifying, and so this essentially justifies us in omitting the whole of τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ, adelphonym and all.³⁶

Eusebius certainly had no qualms about adding information to Josephus to secure identifications and was not always careful in his representations of his source either.³⁷ Additionally, adding these kinds of brief explanatory notes was not unheard of for Eusebius.

³³ Translation from Eusebius, *The Ecclesiastical History*, ed. and trans. Kirsopp Lake, 2 vols. (New York: G. P. Putnam's Sons, 1926), 1:177.

³⁴ In Eusebius, Χριστοῦ comes before λεγομένου while in Josephus it is reversed. The only other difference is that Eusebius writes παρέδωκεν while Josephus has παρέδωκε. These constitute the only differences.

³⁵ Origen previously mentions in *Contra Celsum* 1.47 John the Baptist and explicitly mentions that this reference is in book 18 of *Antiquities*. Thus, the mention of James afterward would be inferred to come after this. There is no one named Jacob/James in book 19 (or book 18), thus it must be book 20, where there are two figures mentioned as such. One is the son of Judas the Galilean (20.102). Thus, the only possibility that remains would be the James of 20.200.

³⁶ Notably, this would also still work with ὄνομα αὐτῶ where people and places are often named standalone with this or some similar variant accompanying it (*Ant.* 1.284; 3.39; 3.54; 3.299; 4.82; 4.161; 4.174; 5.182; 5.207; 5.323; 6.14; 6.32; 6.45; 6.133; 6.171). A prime parallel is *Ant.* 11.198 using ὄνομα αὐτῶ in full to introduce Mordecai (cf. 18.196).

³⁷ To bolster this point, there are other occasions where Eusebius misrepresents Josephus. Olson, "Eusebius and the 'Testimonium Flavianum'," 318–9 lists other examples of Eusebius also attributing false information to Josephus, such as the notion that the fall of Jerusalem occurred at Passover (which Josephus never says). Whealey, "Josephus," 109 is forced to admit that Eusebius does misrepresent Josephus, and even lists an additional example (109n99).

For instance, in *Demonstratio Evangelica* 8.2, Eusebius quotes *Ant.* 20.247–249 but adds an identifier, “the ones who were called the Maccabees,” which is absent in the *textus receptus*.³⁸ As such, we have prior examples of Eusebius conducting this kind of small clarifying interpolation to help his audience.

I propose that Eusebius was the origin of our *textus receptus* version of the passage, having interpolated it on Origen’s authority into our present text of *Antiquities*. The motivation for doing so would be that, while he had this fake quote attributed to Josephus, it would have been rather bothersome that no information which approximated Origen’s description existed in the text. As a result, he added this in at *Ant.* 20.200, which has several cursory similarities both to what Origen describes, and to Christian tradition.³⁹

In my view, it makes better sense to omit the whole of τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ, rather than just λεγομένου Χριστοῦ, as the entire passage appears to be mobile in that tradition and the adelphonym’s style is highly problematic.⁴⁰ Additionally, it would not have been out of the ordinary for Josephus to simply mention some person in passing, without further details or explanation, as noted above. Omitting the entire phrase poses no serious problem and resolves the stylistic issues without needing recourse to the convoluted notion of an adelphonym being applied to this James, referring to a figure only introduced a few lines down (*Ant.* 20.203), which is an entirely unattested phenomenon for Josephan adelphonymics.⁴¹ We likewise have no need to resort to an alternative adelphonym of “son of Damneus” or some other patronymic,⁴² which resolves some other problems caused by the inclusion of λεγομένου Χριστοῦ. If my hypothesis is correct, the reception evidence should likewise point toward Eusebian origin.

ALL ROADS LEAD BACK TO EUSEBIUS: THE RECEPTION

If one were to refute this thesis, they would need to demonstrate clearly non-Eusebian quotations of the passage. As Origen is neither quoting the passage, nor demonstrating any independent knowledge of its contents (as his misrepresentations make clear), we must look elsewhere for attestation.

³⁸ Thanks to Ken Olson for this reference.

³⁹ These would be (1) the mention of a figure named James; (2) this James is stoned to death (cf. Hegesippus and the *Second Apocalypse of James*, the former of which Eusebius mentions, see *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.17); (3) this execution also happens relatively close to when Josephus mentions the fall of Jerusalem in *Ant.* 20.252–265). As such, the identification would have come naturally, as it did for Origen.

⁴⁰ As List explains, it is strange to think that Josephus would be referring, two books later, to an obscure and random figure mentioned in 18.63–64, as if readers would have known him well enough to get the reference, see “The Death of James the Just Revisited,” 21n17.

⁴¹ Pace List, “The Death of James the Just Revisited.”

⁴² Allen, “Josephus on James the Just?” 14 thinks there could be any kind of now-lost patronymic. As List explains (“The Death of James the Just Revisited,” 28n45) this is however entirely unnecessary and overcomplicates the argumentation by suggesting not only interpolation, but deletion. Had “son of Damneus” or some other patronymic existed, it is doubtful that anyone like Origen or Eusebius would have made the mistake.

Perhaps the first question should concern the Greek manuscripts of Josephus' text. Unfortunately, these are already of specious authority, since they contain clearly suspect material, specifically the Christianized *Testimonium Flavianum*, and the earliest manuscript of book 20 is the eleventh century CE.⁴³ Even more specious is that *all* Greek manuscripts derive from the same text family, meaning an interpolation into only one earlier Greek manuscript could account for every Greek manuscript we have today.⁴⁴ Since our Greek manuscripts are so late, one cannot rule out textual harmonization with Eusebius in *Ant.* 20.200, thus they remain unhelpful.

In my view, the few references we have to *Ant.* 20.200 after Eusebius still likely rely upon Eusebius. The first is Jerome, *De Viris Illustribus* 13, who in remarking on Josephus claims that the latter attributed the fall of Jerusalem to the death of James (*et propter interfectionem Iacobi apostoli Hierosolymam dirutam*). Throughout *De Viris Illustribus*, Jerome is almost certainly indebted to Eusebius, which Jerome himself readily acknowledged (*De Viris Illustribus*, praef.3).⁴⁵ The above is only a brief recollection of the passage, but the earlier *De Viris Illustribus* 2 provides us with more detail. Here he mixes the work of Josephus and Clement together, making it clear he is not carefully evaluating Josephus' text. Jerome adds, once again (without quoting), that Josephus claimed James' death caused the fall of Jerusalem. Jerome is probably relying on Eusebius, who is the first author to bring Josephus and Clement into proximity on these matters and who retains the same pseudo-Josephan passage attributing Jerusalem's destruction to James' death which Jerome uses.⁴⁶ As such, we can dismiss Jerome's *De Viris Illustribus*. Similarly, his allusion to the passage in *Adversus Iovinianum* 1.39 can be regarded as unhelpful.⁴⁷

The *Latin Antiquities* is a problem. It is elsewhere known that the *Testimonium Flavianum* was not retranslated when the *Latin Antiquities* was produced; instead, translators cribbed Rufinus' translations from his Latin rendition of Eusebius' *Historia Ecclesiastica*.⁴⁸ We also know that they did not directly copy from Rufinus when they produced their rendition of *Ant.* 20.200,⁴⁹ however a side-by-side comparison illustrates that we cannot rule out potential contamination:⁵⁰

⁴³ See Olson, "Eusebius and the 'Testimonium Flavianum'," 306–7; Clare K. Rothschild, "Echoes of a Whisper: The Uncertain Authenticity of Josephus' Witness to John the Baptist," in *Ablution, Initiation, and Baptism: Late Antiquity, Early Judaism, and Early Christianity*, ed. David Hellholm, 3 vols. (Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 2011), 2.255–90 at 273–74.

⁴⁴ Olson, "Eusebius and the 'Testimonium Flavianum'," 306–7.

⁴⁵ Whealey, *Josephus on Jesus*, 29–30.

⁴⁶ Eusebius, *Historia Ecclesiastica* 2.23.3, 19 (Clement) and 2.23.20–24 (Josephus).

⁴⁷ Emil Schürer, *A History of the Jewish People in the Time of Christ*, trans. John MacPherson, 2 vols. (New York: Charles Scribner's Sons, 1896), 2:187n45.

⁴⁸ Whealey, *Josephus on Jesus*, 34–36.

⁴⁹ Levenson and Martin, "The Latin Translations of Josephus," 58.

⁵⁰ For this table, words in bold are exact. Words in bold and italics share roots.

<i>Latin Antiquities</i> ⁵¹	Rufinus' trans. <i>Historia Ecclesiastica</i> ⁵²
<p>Ananus autem iunior cum pontificatum suscepisset, erat uehementer asperrimus et audax secta Saduceus qui circa iudicia sunt ultra omnes Iudaeos ualde crudeles, sicuti iam declarauimus. Cum ergo huius sectae Ananus esset, credens se inuenisse tempus oportunum, Festo mortuo, et Albino in itinere constituto, concilium fecit iudicum, et quosdam deducens ad semetipsum inter quos et fratrem Ihesu, qui dicitur Christus, nomine Iacobum, quasi contra legem agentes accusans, tradidit lapidandos. Qui autem uidebantur esse moderatissimi ciuitatis, et circa legis integritatem habere sollicitudinem, grauius hoc tulere, miseruntque latenter ad regem rogantes eum, ut scriberet Anano, ne talia perpetraret, cum neque prius recte fecisset.</p>	<p>Ananias autem iunior, quem pontificatum suscepisse supra diximus, proteruus admodum et insolens moribus haeresim defendebat Sadducaeorum, qui in iudiciis crudeliores ceteris Iudaeis videntur, sicut iam supra ostendimus. Hic insolentiae suae tempus datum credens ex morte Festi consessum iudicum convocat et introducit in medium fratrem Iesu, qui dicitur Christus, Iacobum nomine, et alios quam plurimos, quos velut contra legem gerere incusans tradidit lapidandos. Quod facinus si qui ex civibus modestior fuit et aequi ac legis observantior, gravissime tulit. Qui etiam occulte legationem ad Caesarem mittunt, orantes eum scribere Ananiae, ne haec agat, quia neque prius huiusmodi facinora recte commiserit.</p> <p>[The <i>Latin Antiquities</i> use of <i>omnes</i> is paralleled in the Rufinus translation of the Pseudo-Josephus, 2.23.20]</p>

There are several instances of verbal overlap and, notably, the highest volumes of clusters occur at and immediately surrounding the James reference (which itself is almost

⁵¹ The *Latin Antiquities* quotation of 20.199–203 is derived from Levenson and Martin, “The Latin Translations of Josephus,” 47–48.

⁵² The Rufinus translation is from Levenson and Martin, “The Latin Translations of Josephus,” 79 and cross referenced with Eduard Schwartz, ed., *Eusebius Werke: Zweiter Band*, 2 vols. (Leipzig: J. C. Henrichs, 1903), 1.173–75.

identical with Rufinus). A final issue is that Cassiodorus' group probably did not finish their translation of *Antiquities* until the mid-sixth century CE, by which time they easily could have used an interpolated Greek manuscript. This means the *Latin Antiquities* are of little help in finding independent attestation of the James passage.⁵³ Given that the translators utilized Rufinus elsewhere, we can, at best, only say that it is unclear if the passage was contaminated by influence from Rufinus. Therefore, the *Latin Antiquities* cannot stand as an independent witness to the James passage either.

There are other references to this passage as well. George Syncellus refers to it, but his quotation is clearly derived from Eusebius, as it is the passage which Eusebius pulled from Origen and then (falsely) attributed to Josephus.⁵⁴ The *Chronicon Paschale* (PG 92.596) alludes to this passage and even ascribes it to Josephus' *Jewish War* (book five specifically), but contra Olson, the *Chronicon* is probably not independent of Eusebius.⁵⁵ Instead, as Whealey has pointed out, the *Chronicon Paschale* is almost certainly dependent on Eusebius' *Historia Ecclesiastica* and the misattributed quotation.⁵⁶ More problematic is that the passage attests not to the *textus receptus* reading, but PG 92.596, which prefers the more ecclesiastically safe τὸν ἀδελφὸν τοῦ Κυρίου ("brother of the Lord"), derived from Gal. 1:19. This mirrors the allusion to Photius' passage as well. Photius, who betrays no knowledge of the *Testimonium Flavianum*, does write in his *Bibliotheca* fol. 238 that he saw a reference to James but does not quote the passage and refers to James as τὸν ἀδελφὸν τοῦ Κυρίου. Given this, he does not attest to a Greek text which reads τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ specifically.⁵⁷ This means he and the *Chronicon Paschale* remain unhelpful on this subject.⁵⁸

Hamartolos also misattributes Hegesippus' work (which he derived from Eusebius) to Josephus.⁵⁹ Hamartolos' passage on James is almost certainly taken from Eusebius, as it copies

⁵³ This need not have occurred in all either; a marginal gloss or insertion would have been sufficient prior (their translation in fact might have been produced on that basis). This occurred with Rufinus' manuscripts and the aforementioned 'he was believed to be the Christ' emendation of the *Testimonium Flavianum*, see Levenson and Martin, "The Latin Translations of Josephus," 25–26. As such, this certainly has precedent.

⁵⁴ For Syncellus, I am using Barthold Georg Niebuhr, ed., *Corpus Scriptorum Historiae Byzantinae: Georgius Syncellus*, vol. 1 (Bonn: Impensis Ed. Weberi, 1829), 641.

⁵⁵ Olson, "Eusebius and the 'Testimonium Flavianum,'" 318.

⁵⁶ Whealey, "Josephus," 108. One indicator is there is some similar terminology between this and the pseudo-Josephan passage that Eusebius cribbed from Origen. The *Chronicon* probably ascribes this to the *Jewish War* since this did not align with the *Ant.* 20.200 passage Eusebius goes on to quote.

⁵⁷ One additional problem with Photius is that he was certainly familiar with Eusebius' work, as he cites it (*Bibliotheca* fol. 27). He was likewise familiar with Sozomen's *Historia Ecclesiastica*, also reliant on Eusebius. This is particularly problematic as Photius did not create his summaries of other works in a vacuum but frequently melded sources. In his summary of *Antiquities*, he in fact includes additional information from Acts on the death of James the brother of John, which is not found in *Antiquities*. Yet because Photius does not differentiate between sources, everything appears to be from the mouth of Josephus.

⁵⁸ Pace Whealey, "Josephus," 109, Photius simply does not aid us in providing independent attestation. A major issue is that since Book 20 by Photius' time would have been commonly associated with James, he may have found an uninterpolated passage and simply assumed this unknown James was the one everyone referred to previously. Thus, he refers to James as the "brother of the Lord." There is no evidence that he saw the *textus receptus* passage as it currently stands. Thus, Whealey's suggestion in contradiction of Ken Olson is simply unconvincing.

⁵⁹ Whealey, "Josephus," 108–9.

(A) the more legendary account (not Josephus' actual words from 20.200), and (B) some of the peculiarities and surrounding wording from Eusebius, which rules out Origen as the source.⁶⁰ Cedrenus, who is probably dependent on Eusebius via the intermediary of Hamartolos, also references the passage.⁶¹ John Zonaras, *Epitome* 6.17 (PG 134.508–9) paraphrases the *Antiquities* 20.200 passage and not the more legendary account. However, as Christopher T. Mallan observes, “From Augustus onwards imperial history is augmented with church history, derived in the main, from Eusebius for the period up to Constantine the Great.”⁶² There are a few terms that seem to indicate he is paraphrasing from Eusebius' version and not directly reading *Antiquities* here.⁶³ This includes the infamous *Testimonium Flavianum* as well.

The *Suda* (s.v. Ἰώσηπος, iota 503) attributes several claims about James and his death leading to the destruction of the Temple to Josephus (the *Suda* continues with the *Testimonium Flavianum*), as well that John the Baptist was a true prophet. The *Suda* is here clearly deriving this information from the Greek translation of Jerome's *De Viris Illustribus* 13, who makes the same claims, in the exact same order, and (like the *Suda*) with identical language. The *Suda* is therefore not independent of Eusebius.

Lastly, a brief note must be made on the *Sepher Yosippon*. In the Yerahme'el manuscript, there are two additions on Philo and Josephus, the latter of which concerns us. The one on Josephus (which is appended to the end of the text after an interpolated appendix on Titus) contains a reference to James the brother of Jesus, alongside some details on Jesus.⁶⁴ As Steven B. Bowman demonstrates, however, the addition on Josephus was almost certainly composed by Yerahme'el ben Shlomo himself in twelfth century Italy, and probably based

⁶⁰ Using the critical edition from Carl de Boor, *Georgii Monachi Chronicon*, 2 vols. (Leipzig: B. G. Teubner, 1904), 1.379. Here Hamartolos includes δὲ ἀπέκτειναν (the former is absent in Origen), and also has Ἰουδαῖοι before ἀπέκτειναν (absent in Origen) and makes the same combination of συμβέβηκεν which Eusebius renders from Origen's συμβε βηκέναι. He also includes some other surrounding language from Eusebius as well: φησι before ταῦτα, for instance. As such, we can be certain this derives directly from Eusebius.

⁶¹ Whealey, “Josephus,” 109. Cedrenus' *Compendium* (PG 121.401). Like Hamartolos, Cedrenus omits οἱ. However, by far the most compelling is that Cedrenus simply copies Hamartolos' introductory sentences almost verbatim. Cedrenus: θάψαντες δὲ αὐτὸν περὶ τῷ ναῷ ἀνήγειραν τὴν στήλην αὐτοῦ. Μετὰ δὲ μαρτύριον αὐτοῦ παρὰ πόδας πολιορκεῖται Ἰερουσαλήμ· φησι γὰρ Ἰώσηπος. Cf. Hamartolos, *Chronicon*: θάψαντες δὲ αὐτὸν παρὰ τῷ ναῷ ἀνήγειραν αὐτοῦ τὴν στήλην. μετὰ δὲ τὸ μαρτύριον αὐτοῦ παρὰ πόδας Ἰερουσαλήμ πολιορκεῖται. φησι γὰρ Ἰώσηπος.

⁶² Christopher T. Mallan, “The Historian John Zonaras: Some Observations on His Sources and Methods,” in *Sources et modèles des historiens anciens*, ed. Olivier Devillers and Breno Battistin Sebastiani (Bordeaux: Ausonius, 2018), 353–66, at 355.

⁶³ Both frame the story as relating the death of James (θάνατον), both utilize a variant of παραλαμβάνω (Zonaras uses παρελιφῶς and Eusebius παρελιφέναι) after τὴν ἀρχιερωσύνην. This term is absent in Josephus. These seem to indicate reliance on Eusebius. One of the bigger determiners is that he also includes mention of Nero in his version. Eusebius mentions Nero throughout book 2 of *Historia Ecclesiastica*, including in the sections directly before and after chapter 23. While Origen also mentions Nero in proximity to the death of James (*Contra Celsum* 2.13), Origen does not mention Ananus or paraphrase the whole Josephan passage, as Zonaras does. As such, he must be relying on Eusebius as his source here and bringing Nero and James into proximity independent of Origen.

⁶⁴ Steven B. Bowman, *Sepher Yosippon: A Tenth-Century History of Ancient Israel* (Detroit: Wayne State University Press, 2022), 393n1.

on Jerome's *De Viris Illustribus* 2 and 13, which contains much of the same information.⁶⁵ Therefore, this addition which alludes to the James passage is derived from Eusebius via the intermediary of Jerome.

This investigation demonstrates that there appear to be no non-Eusebian, independent witnesses to the James passage (Origen notwithstanding).⁶⁶ Instead, all of these could plausibly be traced back to Eusebius himself (either through direct usage of Eusebius or through intermediaries), making him the most likely candidate for the origination of τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ in our present texts as well. This follows from the *Testimonium Flavianum's* currently known trajectory as well, which traces its roots through Eusebius in all known traditions.⁶⁷

CONCLUSIONS

If my hypothesis is correct, then the following chain of events led to the James passage in *Antiquities* 20.200 existing as we have it today:

(1) Origen, functioning purely from memory and with his own apologetic aims, credits to Josephus the claim that James' death was the cause of the siege of Jerusalem and its destruction. In this, he ascribes the words τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ to Josephus in the *Commentary on Matthew* 10.17 and similar wording from two places in *Contra Celsum* (1.47 and 2.13). The James Origen is thinking of was probably some hitherto unknown figure, simply called "James" without further identifiers, mentioned in *Ant.* 20.200.

(2) Eusebius, on Origen's authority, sees two divergent iterations of the passage in the *Commentary on Matthew* and *Contra Celsum* and ascribes them to Josephus as separate passages. The latter he makes up using the quotations from *Contra Celsum*, while the *Commentary on Matthew's* τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ Eusebius places in *Ant.* 20.200 as it is the only plausible candidate for James. However, Eusebius places τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ *before* the name of James, unlike Origen, because he could not easily insert it after, due to ὄνομα αὐτῶ after James' name.

⁶⁵ Bowman, *Sepher Yosippon*, xiii and 393n1. For more on *Yosippon* and its reception, see Whealey, *Josephus on Jesus*, 58–62.

⁶⁶ Brief mention should also be given to *Suda*, s.v. Ἰησοῦς (iota 229) which attributes even more information to Josephus found in no extant manuscripts, but which probably derives from Origen's claims, particularly *Contra Celsum* 1.47.

⁶⁷ Whealey, "Josephus," 29–30, 34–36 for Jerome and Rufinus; Whealey, "The Testimonium Flavianum in Syriac and Arabic," for Agapius and Michael the Syrian. Whealey's position that Isidore of Pelusium, *Ep.* 4.225 and Pseudo-Hegesippus' *De Excidio* 2.12 are potentially independent witnesses is faulty. Isidore did know of Eusebius' writings, see *Ep.* 2.212 and was likewise familiar with John Chrysostom who used *Demonstratio Evangelica*, see Manfred Kertsch, "Patristische Miscellen," *Vigiliae Christianae* 42, no. 4 (1988): 395–400. Additionally, recent studies show that the *Testimonium Flavianum* in Pseudo-Hegesippus is certainly derived from Eusebius, see Agnès Molinier-Arbo, "Crime et châtement des Juifs. Réminiscences d'Eusèbe de Césarée dans les histoires du pseudo-Hégésippe," *Revue des études latines* 99 (2021): 161–81; David J. DeVore, "On the Fourth-Century Reception of Eusebius's *Ecclesiastical History*," *Church History* 92, no. 3 (2023): 644–50, at 648.

(3) Subsequent scribes all resort to Eusebius for this passage afterward, which is then incorporated into our manuscript traditions. The Latin tradition was probably a result of contamination with Rufinus' translation of Eusebius' *Historia Ecclesiastica*. Meanwhile, the Greek traditions all trace back to Eusebius, either directly or through an intermediary.

This thesis has the benefit of explaining all available data regarding the James passage without resorting to the overly complex theories of other critics, which suggest some kind of marginal gloss insertion or similar.⁶⁸ Instead, all available evidence indicates this could have come about by Eusebius directly. Similarly, there is no need to explain James as being related to the figure Jesus ben Damneus mentioned in 20.203 through some convoluted use of adelphonymics. If my theory is correct, then, James (and the nameless others) are denizens who were subjected to the extreme punishments of Ananus. Who they were, specifically, is unimportant for Josephus' narrative, as he was more interested in illustrating the harshness of Ananus' rule and his upsetting the sensibilities of the respected citizens (*Ant.* 20.201). Given this, I propose omitting the whole of τὸν ἀδελφὸν Ἰησοῦ τοῦ λεγομένου Χριστοῦ.

Now if one does not find the negative case compelling, I believe there are still enough problems listed that the positive case is sufficiently prevented from being found probable. None of the justifications for the "authentic" side stand up to scrutiny. Appealing to the manuscript evidence is faulty, as all quotations and references to the James passage past Eusebius also rely on Eusebius' authority. Further, the phrase λεγομένου Χριστοῦ is frequently found in Christian texts, both in reverential and non-reverential settings (especially in cases where Christian scribes imagine what nonbelievers would write). The argument that they would not refer to James as "the brother of Jesus" out of adherence to the doctrine of the Perpetual Virginity is fallacious,⁶⁹ as it presumes that all Christians (A) would have treated the virginity of Mary the same, which is untrue as many did not hold to her perpetual virginity (Eusebius himself does not outwardly attest to his own adherence to this⁷⁰), and (B) that they went around performing all interpolations with intense piety that ought be reflected in said interpolations. Neither should be accepted flatly.

Because we already know that *Antiquities* was altered by Christian scribes, we are at least justified in taking an agnostic position; we simply cannot tell whether this portion of text is authentic or not. Given Josephus' usage of adelphonyms, this gives us even more reason to tie *Ant.* 20.200 to a passage with known Christian tampering. Given this, the burden of proof is now on those who assert authenticity to defend it, as we have ample reasons to dismiss their position. This has ramifications for biblical studies and beyond, as this removes Josephus from giving any reliable early attestation to the life of Jesus or to the martyrdom of James, leaving only the unreliable later Church Traditions as evidence of James' death.

⁶⁸ List, 'The Death of James the Just Revisited'; Allen, 'Josephus on James the Just?'; Carrier, 'Origen, Eusebius, and the Accidental Interpolation'.

⁶⁹ Whealey, "Josephus," 111–5 makes this argument unconvincingly.

⁷⁰ Which Whealey is forced to concede, see Whealey, "Josephus," 113.

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